

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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Table 1. Techniques for semantic similarity and rare event detection in text data under differential privacy (RQ.3).

Cluster A: Vector-Based and Embedding Techniques	
Technique	Studies
ClinicalBERT	[Hu et al. 2024]
D2V	[Shahmirzadi et al. 2019]
Doc2vec-CNN-based	[Qin et al. 2025]
ERNIE Model	[Wang et al. 2020]
GloVe	[P. and Shaji 2019, Zhu et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020]
LSI	[Shahmirzadi et al. 2019]
Scientific BERT (SciBERT)	[Hu et al. 2024]
Sentence-BERT (SBERT)	[Stanik et al. 2021]
Universal Sentence Encoder (USE)	[Devine et al. 2021]
Vector	[Benard Magara et al. 2018, Gambarelli et al. 2023, Stanik et al. 2021, Zhu et al. 2021, Wang et al. 2016, Wang et al. 2018, Shahmirzadi et al. 2019, Sitikhu et al. 2019, Lam et al. 2017, Eminagaoglu and Goksen 2020]
Vector Space Model (VSM)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Vectorized Term Frequency	[Roul et al. 2017]
Word Analogy	[Zhu et al. 2021]
Word Embeddings	[Devine et al. 2021, Stanik et al. 2021, Zhu et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020, enel et al. 2018, P. and Shaji 2019, Meyer et al. 2023, Hassan et al. 2019, Abdalla et al. 2020b, Abdalla et al. 2020a, van Baal et al. 2025, Nguyen et al. 2015]
Word2Vec	[Xu et al. 2019, Zhu et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020, Shahmirzadi et al. 2019, Sitikhu et al. 2019, P. and Shaji 2019]
Word Mover	[Sitikhu et al. 2019]
Word Similarity	[Zhu et al. 2021]
Word Vector Model	[Sitikhu et al. 2019]
Cluster B: Topic Modeling and Probabilistic Approaches	
Technique	Studies
Author Topic Model (ATM)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Aspect and Sentiment Unification Model (ASUM)	[Stanik et al. 2021]
Bitern Topic Model (BTM)	[Stanik et al. 2021]
Focused Topic Model (FTM)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)	[Stanik et al. 2021, Xu et al. 2019, Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020, Wang et al. 2016, Lam et al. 2017, Alhawarat and Hegazi 2018, Poria et al. 2016, Aiello et al. 2013, Nguyen et al. 2015, Li et al. 2011, Gualberto et al. 2020, enel et al. 2018]
Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA)	[Zhu et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020, Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020, Wang et al. 2016, Lam et al. 2017, P. and Shaji 2019, enel et al. 2018]
LDAH	[Wang et al. 2016]
LSAH	[Wang et al. 2016]
LDAHGW	[Wang et al. 2016]
LDAHW	[Wang et al. 2016]
Partially Labeled Topic Model (PLDA)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Tag-LDA Model	[Wang et al. 2016]
Tag-Weighted Dirichlet Allocation (TWDAL)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Tag-Weighted Topic Model (TWTM)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Topic Model with Biased Propagation (TMBP)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Topic Modeling	[Stanik et al. 2021]
Word Intrusion	[enel et al. 2018]

Cluster C: Similarity and Distance Measures	
Technique	Studies
Adjacency Matrix	[Saeed et al. 2020]
Angular Separation	[Shahmirzadi et al. 2019]
Averaged Kullback-Leibler Divergence	[Froud et al. 2010]
BM25 Term Weighting	[Zhang et al. 2010]
Cosine Similarity	[Zaware et al. 2021, Benard Magara et al. 2018, Saeed et al. 2020, Shahmirzadi et al. 2019, Sitikhu et al. 2019, Froud et al. 2010, Eminagaoglu and Goksen 2020]
Euclidean Distance	[Benard Magara et al. 2018]
Hellinger Principal Component Analysis (H-PCA)	[Zhu et al. 2021]
Jaccard Similarity	[Benard Magara et al. 2018]
Jensen-Shannon Distance	[Sitikhu et al. 2019]
Pearson Coefficient	[Benard Magara et al. 2018]
TF (Term Frequency)	[Sitikhu et al. 2019, Yin et al. 2012, Zaware et al. 2021, Aiello et al. 2013, Bleik et al. 2013]
Term Frequency(TF)	[Zaware et al. 2021, Bleik et al. 2013, Aiello et al. 2013, Sitikhu et al. 2019, Yin et al. 2012]
Inverse Document Frequency(IDF)	[Sitikhu et al. 2019, Yin et al. 2012]
Term FrequencyInverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF)	[Zaware et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020, Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020, Roul et al. 2017]

Cluster D: Classification and Clustering Algorithms	
Technique	Studies
APDPk-means	[Fan and Xu 2019]
AR-Miner	[Stanik et al. 2021]
Clustering	[Stanik et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020, Wang et al. 2016, Guan et al. 2011, Fan and Xu 2019]
Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)	[Chen et al. 2019, Qin et al. 2025]
Decision Trees	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Differential Privacy k-means	[Fan and Xu 2019]
HDBSCAN	[Tarek et al. 2024]
K-means Clustering (KMC)	[Saeed et al. 2020, Alhawarat and Hegazi 2018, Guan et al. 2011, Fan and Xu 2019]
k-NN Classification	[Gambarelli et al. 2023, Eminagaoglu and Goksen 2020]
kNN (sk-kNN - Set-Based-kernel k-NN Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
k-NN (lk-kNN - Linear-kernel k-NN Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
k-NN (t-kNN - Text-based k-NN Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	[Asimopoulos et al. 2024, Shih et al. 2017]
Naïve Bayes (NB) classification	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Naïve Bayes (NB) (t-NB - Text-based NB Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Random Forest(RF) and Boosted	[Benard Magara et al. 2018]
Recursive PARTitioning (RPART)	[Benard Magara et al. 2018]
Siamese LSTM	[Shih et al. 2017]
Support Vector Machine (SVM)	[Bleik et al. 2013, Gambarelli et al. 2023, Mehta et al. 2019]
SVM (sk-SVM - Set-Based-kernel SVM Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
SVM (lk-SVM - Linear-kernel SVM Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
SVM (t-SVM - Text-based SVM Classifier)	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Seeds Affinity Propagation (SAP)	[Guan et al. 2011]
UMAP	[Tarek et al. 2024]
XGBoost	[Gualberto et al. 2020]

Cluster E: Text Preprocessing and Linguistic Techniques	
Technique	Studies
Bag of Words (BoW)	[Gambarelli et al. 2023, Wang et al. 2016]
Concept Labeling	[Yu et al. 2016, Hua et al. 2015]
Controlled Vocabulary	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Cross-Lingual Studies	[enel et al. 2018]
Document-Term Matrix (DTM)	[Gualberto et al. 2020]
Lemmatization	[Gualberto et al. 2020]
Named Entity Recognition (NER)	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020, Yu et al. 2016, Hua et al. 2017, Hua et al. 2015, enel et al. 2018]
N-gram	[Aiello et al. 2013]
Part-of-Speech Tagging	[Yu et al. 2016, Hua et al. 2017, Hua et al. 2015, enel et al. 2018]
Relation Extraction (RE)	[Wang et al. 2020]
Semantically Enhanced Aspect Extraction (SEAE)	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]
Semantic Labeling	[Hua et al. 2017]
Sentiment Analysis	[enel et al. 2018]
Short Text Understanding	[Liang et al. 2018, Yu et al. 2016, Hua et al. 2017, Wang et al. 2016, Hua et al. 2015]
Summarized Parallel Corpus (SPC)	[Saeed et al. 2020]
Summary	[Stanik et al. 2021]
Text Segmentation	[Yu et al. 2016, Hua et al. 2017, Hua et al. 2015]
Text Summarization	[Saeed et al. 2020]
Word Sense Disambiguation	[enel et al. 2018]
Wordclouds	[van Baal et al. 2025]

Cluster F: Graph-based and Network Approaches	
Technique	Studies
Graph Creation	[Zaware et al. 2021, Saeed et al. 2020, Stanik et al. 2021, Wang et al. 2016]
Graph Kernel	[Bleik et al. 2013]
Hashtag Graph-based Topic Model (HGTM)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Hashtag Clustering	[Wang et al. 2016]
KUSH	[Saeed et al. 2020]
PageRank Algorithm	[Saeed et al. 2020]
Sentence Ranking	[Zaware et al. 2021]
Textrank	[Zaware et al. 2021]
Topic Intrusion	[Stanik et al. 2021]

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